

4.6.3 Power consumption.

Table 37: Power consumption.

Voltage	Current	Fuse
+5 V	3 A	10 A
-5.2 V	10 A	15 A
-2 V	5 A	10 A
-15 V	0.5 A	2 A

Table 36: Trigger Control Line

pins (+/-)	New connector C2		Old connector N9	
	signal	I/O	signal	I/O
1,20	GBL	O	GBL	O
2,21	FE_RDY	O	FE_RDY	O
3,22	GND	-	GND	-
4,23	-	-	-	-
5,24	LABEL(1)	I	T_O	I
6,25	LABEL(0)	I	COS_ENB	I
7,26	T2_YES	I	T2_YES	I
8,27	T2_NO	I	T2_NO	I
9,28	T1_YES	I	T1_YES	I
10,29	T1_NO	I	T1_NO	I
11,30	e ⁺ pick-up	I	TEST	
12,31	e ⁻ pick-up	I	COSMIC	
13,32	CLK_BCO	I	CLK_BCO	I
14,33	WNG_BCO	I	WNG_BCO	I
15,34	GND	-	GND	-
16,35	RF3	I	RF3	I
17,36	GND	-	GND	-
18,37	-	-	RF2	I
19	GND	-	-	-

NOTE: The old Pandora connectors N5, N6, N10 are suppressed, N8 is replaced by a single twisted pairs connector.

Table 35: NEI_DONE

New connector C6			Old connector N4		
pins (+/-)	signal	I/O	pins (-/+)	signal	I/O
1,2	NEI_DONE(0)	I	1,2	NEI_DONE(0)	I
3,4	NEI_DONE(1)	I	3,4	NEI_DONE(1)	I
5,6	NEI_DONE(2)	I	5,6	NEI_DONE(2)	I
7,8	NEI_DONE(3)	I	7,8	NEI_DONE(3)	I
9,10	NEI_DONE(4)	I	9,10	NEI_DONE(4)	I
11,12	NEI_DONE(5)	I	11,12	NEI_DONE(5)	I
13,14	NEI_DONE(6)	I	13,14	NEI_DONE(6)	I
15,16	NEI_DONE(7)	I	15,16	NEI_DONE(7)	I
17,18	NEI_DONE(8)	I	17,18	NEI_DONE(8)	I
19,20	NEI_DONE(9)	I	19,20	NEI_DONE(9)	I
21,22	NEI_DONE(10)	I	21,22	NEI_DONE(10)	I
23,14	NEI_DONE(11)	I	23,14	NEI_DONE(11)	I
25,26	NEI_DONE(12)	I	25,26	NEI_DONE(12)	I
27,28	NEI_DONE(13)	I	27,28	NEI_DONE(13)	I
29,30	NEI_DONE(14)	I	29,30	NEI_DONE(14)	I
31,32	NEI_DONE(15)	I	31,32	NEI_DONE(15)	I
33,34	GND	-	33,34	GND	-

Attention: The pins polarity is inverted.

Table 34: Accounting #

pins (+/-)	New connector C5		Old connector N7	
	signal	I/O	signal	I/O
1,2	ACC#(0)	O	ACC#(0)	O
3,4	ACC#(1)	O	ACC#(1)	O
5,6	ACC#(2)	O	ACC#(2)	O
7,8	ACC#(3)	O	ACC#(3)	O
9,10	GND	-	ACC#(4)	O
11,12			ACC#(5)	O
13,14			ACC#(6)	O
15,16			ACC#(7)	O
17,18			GND	-

Table 32: TCL (Trigger Control Lines)

pins (+ /-)	New connector C4		Old connector N2	
	signal	I/O	signal	I/O
1,2	GND	-	TRIG_ENB	O
3,4	T1_NO	O	T1_NO	O
5,6	T1_YES	O	T1_YES	O
7,8	T2_NO	O	T2_NO	O
9,10	T2_YES	O	T2_YES	O

Table 33: LTCL (Local Trigger Control Lines)

pins (+ /-)	New connector C3		Old connector N3	
	signal	I/O	signal	I/O
1,2	GND	-	GOOT_T2	O
3,4	TRIG_ENB	O	T1_NO_I	I
5,6	T1_NO_I	I	T1_YES_I	I
7,8	T1_YES_I	I	T2_NO_I	I
9,10	T2_NO_I	I	T2_YES_I	I
11,12	T2_YES_I	I		
13,14	GND	-		

- Interleaved cosmic mode.
 - Freeze on error.
- * 16. Ext_Start_Trigger must be synchronous.
- * 17. Former T2_Yes is now called FEF.
- * 18. Internal Rf generator.

4.6.2 Connectors differences

Table 31: WNG's and CLK's

pins (+/-)	New connector C1		Old connector N1	
	signal	I/O	signal	I/O
13	GND	-	-	-
12,25	WNG0	O	GND	-
11,24	WNG1	O	WNG0	O
10,23	WNG2	O	WNG1	O
9,22	WNG3	O	WNG2	O
8,21	WNG4	O	WNG3	O
7,20	GND	-	CLK1	O
6,19	CLK0	O	CLK2	O
5,18	GND	-	CLK3	O
4,17	CLK1	O	-	-
3,16	GND	-	-	-
2,15	CLK2	O	-	-
1,14	GND	-	-	-

4.6 Old and New LTS Differences.

4.6.1 Basic differences

The following is a list of differences between the new (Pand2) and the old Pandora.

1. FB Power requirements: Pand2 needs: +5, -2, -5.2, -15 DC volt. The -15 volt is used to stabilize the power distribution within the module.
- * 2. Front panel connectivity. Detailed comparison is done in section 4.6.2.
- * 3. CSR register definition: The new CSR implementation is different from the old Pandora. Section 4.1 gives details of the new CSR map and bit assignment.
- * 4. Hand shake block transfer (MS=1) to CSR space is only allowed for the T1/T2 look-up table (CSR C000-0010). The incrementing register is CSR C000-000F. No DMA transfer is allowed from FIP.
5. In response to a Stop, Pand2 ends the ongoing cycle with the trigger protocol then stops. Reset forces the State Machine to “wait for start seq” regardless to the trigger protocol.
- * 6. Signal protocol (T1,... T2,...) is strictly enforced due to the presence of the “State Machine”. In particular a T2 decision preceding a T1 decision has no effect.
7. There is no cosmic or time-out scaler.
8. Clocks and warnings are reset at T1_NO, T2_NO or NEI_DONE.
9. Free running clocks are always present, therefore there is no programmable delay before “Start”. Free running clock can be individually disabled (see paragraph 2 for details).
10. All clocks are 50% duty cycle.
11. Pand2 has a 4-bit hardware account # and an internal 8-bit counter incremented by T2_YES.
12. Bad quality of external signal i.e. RF3, C_BCO, W_BCO can cause the PLL to desynchronize. In the old Pandora there would be no observable immediate warning, the effect would be observed later on in the quality of the data!
13. Pand2 has four external trigger input, none has programmable delay.
14. Jitter free operation requires the external trigger to be phase locked to W_BCO, see section 2.1.1 for details.
15. Discarded features:
 - Internal logic analyzer.
 - Switch mode operation.

FIGURE 9. Protocol with readout FIP.

FIGURE 10. Protocol with local-trigger box.

T1NO

T2YES/NO

4.5 Timing diagrams.

FIGURE 8. Protocol with Zeus.

T1NO

T1YES - T2NO

T1YES- T2YES

TABLE 30. NOT Harmonics of the BCO freq.

Freq. [MHz]	period [ns]	N	P	Obs.:
37.6499	26.5605	93	1	kb not 8,
38.4596	26.0013	95	1	kb not 8,
39.2692	25.4652	97	1	kb not 8,
40.0789	24.9508	99	1	kb not 8,
40.8885	24.4567	101	1	kb not 8,
41.6983	23.9818	103	1	kb not 8,
42.5079	23.5250	105	1	kb not 8,
43.3176	23.0853	107	1	kb not 8,
44.1273	22.6617	109	1	kb not 8,
44.9370	22.2534	111	1	kb not 8,
45.7467	21.8595	113	1	kb not 8,
46.5563	21.4794	115	1	kb not 8,
47.3660	21.1122	117	1	kb not 8,
48.1756	20.7574	119	1	kb not 8,
48.9854	20.4143	121	1	kb not 8,
49.7950	20.0823	123	1	kb not 8,
50.6047	19.7610	125	1	kb not 8,
51.4144	19.4498	127	1	kb not 8,
52.2241	19.1483	129	1	kb not 8,
53.0338	18.8559	131	1	kb not 8,
53.8434	18.5724	133	1	kb not 8,
54.6531	18.2972	135	1	kb not 8,
55.4627	18.0301	137	1	kb not 8,
56.2725	17.7707	139	1	kb not 8,
57.0821	17.5186	141	1	kb not 8,
57.8918	17.2736	143	1	kb not 8,
58.7015	17.0353	145	1	kb not 8,
59.5111	16.8036	147	1	kb not 8,
60.3209	16.5780	149	1	kb not 8,
61.1305	16.3585	151	1	kb not 8,
61.9402	16.1446	153	1	kb not 8,
62.7498	15.9363	155	1	kb not 8,
63.5596	15.7333	157	1	kb not 8,
64.3692	15.5354	159	1	kb not 8,
65.1789	15.3424	161	1	kb not 8,
65.9885	15.1542	163	1	kb not 8,
66.7982	14.9705	165	1	kb not 8,
67.6080	14.7912	167	1	kb not 8,
68.4176	14.6161	169	1	kb not 8,
69.2273	14.4452	171	1	kb not 8,
70.0369	14.2782	173	1	kb not 8,
70.8466	14.1150	175	1	kb not 8.

TABLE 30. NOT Harmonics of the BCO freq.

Freq. [MHz]	period [ns]	N	P	Obs.:
24.6950	40.4940	122	2	kb not 8,
24.8974	40.1648	123	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
25.3024	39.5220	125	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
25.5048	39.2084	126	2	kb not 8,
25.7072	38.8997	127	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
26.1120	38.2966	129	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
26.3144	38.0021	130	2	kb not 8,
26.5169	37.7118	131	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
26.9217	37.1448	133	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
27.1241	36.8676	134	2	kb not 8,
27.3265	36.5945	135	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
27.7313	36.0603	137	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
27.9338	35.7989	138	2	kb not 8,
28.1362	35.5414	139	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
28.5410	35.0373	141	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
28.7434	34.7906	142	2	kb not 8,
28.9458	34.5473	143	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
29.3508	34.0707	145	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
29.5532	33.8373	146	2	kb not 8,
29.7556	33.6072	147	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
30.1604	33.1561	149	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
30.3628	32.9351	150	2	kb not 8,
30.5652	32.7170	151	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
30.9701	32.2892	153	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
31.1725	32.0795	154	2	kb not 8,
31.3749	31.8726	155	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
31.7797	31.4666	157	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
31.9821	31.2675	158	2	kb not 8,
32.1845	31.0708	159	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
32.5894	30.6848	161	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
32.7918	30.4954	162	2	kb not 8,
32.9943	30.3083	163	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
33.3991	29.9410	165	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
33.6015	29.7606	166	2	kb not 8,
33.8040	29.5823	167	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
34.2088	29.2323	169	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
34.4112	29.0603	170	2	kb not 8,
34.6136	28.8904	171	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
35.0184	28.5564	173	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
35.2209	28.3922	174	2	kb not 8,
35.4233	28.2300	175	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
36.0305	27.7542	89	1	kb not 8,
36.8403	27.1442	91	1	kb not 8,

TABLE 30. NOT Harmonics of the BCO freq.

Freq. [MHz]	period [ns]	N	P	Obs.:
13.1571	76.0044	130	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
13.3596	74.8523	132	3	kb not 8,
13.5620	73.7352	134	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
13.9669	71.5981	138	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
14.1693	70.5753	140	3	kb not 8,
14.3717	69.5814	142	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
14.7766	67.6746	146	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
14.9790	66.7602	148	3	kb not 8,
15.1814	65.8701	150	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
15.5862	64.1593	154	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
15.7886	63.3368	156	3	kb not 8,
15.9910	62.5352	158	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
16.3959	60.9908	162	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
16.5983	60.2470	164	3	kb not 8,
16.8007	59.5212	166	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
17.2055	58.1208	170	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
17.4079	57.4451	172	3	kb not 8,
17.6105	56.7844	174	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
18.0153	55.5085	89	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
18.2177	54.8918	90	2	kb not 8,
18.4201	54.2886	91	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
18.8249	53.1212	93	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
19.0273	52.5561	94	2	kb not 8,
19.2298	52.0026	95	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
19.6346	50.9305	97	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
19.8370	50.4108	98	2	kb not 8,
20.0394	49.9017	99	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
20.4442	48.9136	101	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
20.6467	48.4338	102	2	kb not 8,
20.8491	47.9636	103	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
21.2539	47.0501	105	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
21.4563	46.6063	106	2	kb not 8,
21.6588	46.1707	107	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
22.0637	45.3234	109	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
22.2661	44.9114	110	2	kb not 8,
22.4685	44.5068	111	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
22.8733	43.7191	113	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
23.0757	43.3357	114	2	kb not 8,
23.2781	42.9588	115	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
23.6830	42.2244	117	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
23.8854	41.8665	118	2	kb not 8,
24.0878	41.5148	119	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
24.4926	40.8286	121	2	kb not 4, 8,12,36,

4.4.2 Frequencies that are not (for all k_b) harmonics of the bco frequency.

In this case N is not a multiple of 2^P . Still, depending on the k_b value, the total product (formula 1) may give an integer number, in which case the clock output will work properly. But be warned: it will be impossible to produce the correct output clock frequency when k_b changes to a value for which formula 1 is not integer any-more! There are a total of 158 different frequencies and for each of them the values of k_b for which it is impossible to produce a correct output frequency are given. The same note as in 4.3.1 is applicable here.

In the following table the value of k_b considered are 4, 8, 12, 18, and 36

TABLE 30. NOT Harmonics of the BCO freq.

Freq. [MHz]	period [ns]	N	P	Obs.:
5.0604	197.6119	50	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
5.2628	190.0119	52	3	kb not 8,
5.4652	182.9749	54	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
5.8702	170.3533	58	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
6.0726	164.6753	60	3	kb not 8,
6.2750	159.3636	62	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
6.6798	149.7059	66	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
6.8822	145.3031	68	3	kb not 8,
7.0846	141.1518	70	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
7.4895	133.5204	74	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
7.6919	130.0070	76	3	kb not 8,
7.8943	126.6737	78	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
8.2991	120.4949	82	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
8.5015	117.6262	84	3	kb not 8,
8.7039	114.8909	86	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
9.1088	109.7835	90	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
9.3112	107.3971	92	3	kb not 8,
9.5136	105.1122	94	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
9.9184	100.8223	98	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
10.1208	98.8059	100	3	kb not 8,
10.3234	96.8676	102	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
10.7282	93.2125	106	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
10.9306	91.4865	108	3	kb not 8,
11.1330	89.8232	110	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
11.5378	86.6717	114	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
11.7403	85.1767	116	3	kb not 8,
11.9427	83.7331	118	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
12.3475	80.9880	122	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,
12.5499	79.6818	124	3	kb not 8,
12.7523	78.4171	126	3	kb not 4, 8,12,36,

TABLE 29. Harmonics of the BCO freq.

Freq. [MHz]	period [ns]	N	P	Freq. [MHz]	period [ns]	N	P
81.7772	12.2283	101	0	82.5869	12.1085	102	0
83.3966	11.9909	103	0	84.2063	11.8756	104	0
85.0159	11.7625	105	0	85.8256	11.6515	106	0
86.6354	11.5426	107	0	87.4450	11.4358	108	0
88.2547	11.3308	109	0	89.0643	11.2278	110	0
89.8740	11.1267	111	0	90.6836	11.0273	112	0
91.4934	10.9298	113	0	92.3030	10.8339	114	0
93.1127	10.7397	115	0	93.9224	10.6471	116	0
94.7321	10.5561	117	0	95.5418	10.4666	118	0
96.3514	10.3787	119	0	97.1611	10.2922	120	0
97.9707	10.2071	121	0	98.7805	10.1235	122	0
99.5901	10.0412	123	0	100.3998	9.9602	124	0
101.2094	9.8805	125	0	102.0191	9.8021	126	0
102.8289	9.7249	127	0	103.6385	9.6489	128	0
104.4482	9.5741	129	0	105.2578	9.5005	130	0
106.0676	9.4280	131	0	106.8772	9.3565	132	0
107.6869	9.2862	133	0	108.4965	9.2169	134	0
109.3062	9.1486	135	0	110.1160	9.0813	136	0
110.9256	9.0151	137	0	111.7353	8.9497	138	0
112.5449	8.8853	139	0	113.3547	8.8219	140	0
114.1643	8.7593	141	0	114.9740	8.6976	142	0
115.7836	8.6368	143	0	116.5933	8.5768	144	0
117.4031	8.5177	145	0	118.2127	8.4593	146	0
119.0224	8.4018	147	0	119.8320	8.3450	148	0
120.6417	8.2890	149	0	121.4514	8.2337	150	0
122.2611	8.1792	151	0	123.0707	8.1254	152	0
123.8804	8.0723	153	0	124.6900	8.0199	154	0
125.4998	7.9681	155	0	126.3095	7.9171	156	0
127.1191	7.8666	157	0	127.9288	7.8168	158	0
128.7384	7.7677	159	0	129.5482	7.7191	160	0
130.3578	7.6712	161	0	131.1675	7.6238	162	0
131.9771	7.5771	163	0	132.7868	7.5309	164	0
133.5966	7.4852	165	0	134.4062	7.4401	166	0
135.2159	7.3956	167	0	136.0255	7.3516	168	0
136.8353	7.3081	169	0	137.6449	7.2651	170	0
138.4546	7.2226	171	0	139.2642	7.1806	172	0
140.0739	7.1391	173	0	140.8837	7.0981	174	0
141.6933	7.0575	175	0	--	--	--	

TABLE 29. Harmonics of the BCO freq.

Freq. [MHz]	period [ns]	N	P	Freq. [MHz]	period [ns]	N	P
12.1451	82.3377	120	3	12.9547	77.1919	128	3
13.7645	72.6509	136	3	14.5741	68.6150	144	3
15.3838	65.0035	152	3	16.1935	61.7531	160	3
17.0031	58.8127	168	3	17.8129	56.1392	88	2
18.6225	53.6986	92	2	19.4322	51.4610	96	2
20.2418	49.4027	100	2	21.0515	47.5025	104	2
21.8612	45.7432	108	2	22.6709	44.1094	112	2
23.4806	42.5883	116	2	24.2902	41.1688	120	2
25.1000	39.8407	124	2	25.9096	38.5958	128	2
26.7193	37.4261	132	2	27.5289	36.3255	136	2
28.3386	35.2875	140	2	29.1482	34.3074	144	2
29.9580	33.3801	148	2	30.7676	32.5017	152	2
31.5773	31.6683	156	2	32.3870	30.8765	160	2
33.1967	30.1235	164	2	34.0064	29.4062	168	2
34.8160	28.7224	172	2	35.6257	28.0696	88	1
36.4353	27.4459	90	1	37.2451	26.8492	92	1
38.0547	26.2780	94	1	38.8644	25.7305	96	1
39.6741	25.2053	98	1	40.4837	24.7013	100	1
41.2935	24.2169	102	1	42.1031	23.7512	104	1
42.9128	23.3031	106	1	43.7224	22.8716	108	1
44.5322	22.4557	110	1	45.3418	22.0547	112	1
46.1515	21.6678	114	1	46.9612	21.2942	116	1
47.7708	20.9333	118	1	48.5806	20.5844	120	1
49.3902	20.2469	122	1	50.1999	19.9204	124	1
51.0095	19.6042	126	1	51.8192	19.2978	128	1
52.6289	19.0010	130	1	53.4386	18.7131	132	1
54.2482	18.4338	134	1	55.0579	18.1627	136	1
55.8677	17.8994	138	1	56.6773	17.6438	140	1
57.4870	17.3952	142	1	58.2966	17.1537	144	1
59.1063	16.9187	146	1	59.9159	16.6900	148	1
60.7257	16.4675	150	1	61.5353	16.2508	152	1
62.3450	16.0398	154	1	63.1547	15.8341	156	1
63.9644	15.6337	158	1	64.7741	15.4383	160	1
65.5837	15.2477	162	1	66.3934	15.0617	164	1
67.2030	14.8803	166	1	68.0128	14.7031	168	1
68.8224	14.5302	170	1	69.6321	14.3612	172	1
70.4418	14.1961	174	1	71.2514	14.0348	88	0
72.0612	13.8771	89	0	72.8708	13.7229	90	0
73.6805	13.5721	91	0	74.4901	13.4246	92	0
75.2999	13.2802	93	0	76.1095	13.1390	94	0
76.9192	13.0007	95	0	77.7288	12.8652	96	0
78.5385	12.7326	97	0	79.3483	12.6027	98	0
80.1579	12.4754	99	0	80.9676	12.3506	100	0

below. Only the values of $M = 5, 29,$ and 145 are possible for all bunches. Since it is desirable that the output clock frequency be “usable” (i.e. be a harmonic of bco frequency and thus have constant phase to bco time) independent of machine operation mode, M has to be one of these three values.

We choose the largest value of M (i.e. 145 since this determines the step (809 KHz) by which we can program the output clock frequency. The value of M is jumpered on the board

TABLE 28. Possible values of M for each k_b

Bunches	M															
	2	3	4	5	6	9	10	15	18	20	29	30	45	58	87	145
4	2	3		5	6	9		15	18		29	30	45	58	87	145
8		3		5		9		15			29		45		87	145
12	2	3		5	6		10	15			29	30		58	87	145
18	2		4	5			10			20	29			58		145
36	2			5			10				29			58		145

The condition on the previous factor $N/2^P = \text{integer}$, will simply put a constraint on the programmable values of N and P (i.e. N must be a multiple of 2^P). The obtainable frequencies are given in the list of paragraph 4.3.1.

Other N and P values are possible even if $N/2^P$ is not an integer, only h has to be integer. However these values are not recommended because they may produce a bad behavior of the output clock depending on the k_b value. A list of these frequencies is given in 4.3.2.

4.4 Possible output frequencies for $M=145$.

4.4.1 Frequencies that are harmonics of the bco frequency (any k_b).

In this case N is a multiple of 2^P . The following list contains 169 frequencies. Note: a given frequency can be obtained with different sets of (N,P) values (e.g $(50,0)$ produces the same result as $(100,1)$). Only the solution with the highest N is given in this list, since the PLL has optimal working point with high N values.

TABLE 29. Harmonics of the BCO freq.

Freq. [MHz]	period [ns]	N	P	Freq. [MHz]	period [ns]	N	P
5.6676	176.4405	56	3	6.4774	154.3839	64	3
7.2870	137.2312	72	3	8.0967	123.5071	80	3
8.9064	112.2784	88	3	9.7160	102.9226	96	3
10.5258	95.0049	104	3	11.3354	88.2193	112	3

4.3 Constraints on generated frequencies.

Only certain values for M, N, and P give a correct synchronization of the generated clocks with respect to the LEP machine cycle. The following considerations apply:

1. Due to the PLLs the clocks are fractions of RF /3 (fig.7). Thus:

$$clock = N * (Rf / 3) / (M * 2^P);$$

2. If the clocks have to be harmonics of the bco frequency, then:

$$clock = h * bco_freq \quad \text{with h integer,}$$

where:

$$bco_freq = (RF * k_b) / 31320$$

with: RF = 352254170 Hz, k_b = number of bunches in LEP and $31320 = 2^3 * 3^3 * 5 * 29$ (the harmonic number or the number of RF oscillations per revolution period in LEP).

FIGURE 7. Basic Block diagram of frequency generation circuit.

This results in the following constraint on M, N and P:

$$N * (2^3 * 3^3 * 5 * 29) / (3 * k_b * M * 2^P) = h \text{ an integer (formula 1)}$$

This condition is certainly met when both factors:

$$N / 2^P \quad \text{and} \quad (2^3 * 3^3 * 5 * 29) / (3 * k_b * M)$$

are integers.

Consider the second factor for the different possibilities of bunches in LEP, i.e. $k_b=4, 8, 12, 18, 36$. The list of possible values of M for each k_b are given in the table

4.2.3 CSR register to Time (WNG4).

CSR C000_000A

bits <14..0> = *LEcounter*

bits <30..16> = *TEcounter*

$$LEdelay = LEOffset + 29 (LEcounter) TimeStep$$

$$TEdelay = TEOffset + 29 (LEcounter + TEcounter) TimeStep$$

Note: This formula is valid for LE and TE counters greater than zero.

4.2.4 Time to CSR register (WNG4).

CSR C000_000A

bits <14..0> = *LEcounter*

bits <30..16> = *TEcounter*

$$LEcounter = \text{floor}\left(\frac{LEdelay - LEOffset}{29TimeStep}\right)$$

$$TEcounter = \text{floor}\left(\frac{TEdelay - TEOffset}{29TimeStep} - LEcounter\right)$$

Note: This formula is valid for LE/TE counter greater than zero.

4.2.1 CSR register to Time (WNG0, WNG1, WNG2, WNG3, CLK0, CLK1, CLK2).

WNG0 / WNG1 / WNG2 / WNG3 (CSR C000_0000 to C000_0003)

bits <2..0> = *LEphase* [A..E]

bits <13..3> = *LEcounter*

bits <18..16> = *TEphase* [A..E]

bits <29..19> = *TEcounter*

CLK0 / CLK1 / CLK2 / Trig_Enable (CSR C000_0004 to C000_0006, C000_000E)

bits <2..0> = *LEphase* [A..E]

bits <13..3> = *LEcounter*

$$LEdelay = LEOffset + (5LEcounter + LEphase) TimeStep$$

$$TEdelay = TEOffset + (5LEcounter + 5TEcounter + TEphase) TimeStep$$

4.2.2 Time to CSR register (WNG0, WNG1, WNG2, WNG3, CLK0, CLK1, CLK2).

WNG0 / WNG1 / WNG2 / WNG3 (CSR C000_0000 to C000_0003)

bits <2..0> = *LEphase* [A..E]

bits <13..3> = *LEcounter*

bits <18..16> = *TEphase* [A..E]

bits <29..19> = *TEcounter*

CLK0 / CLK1 / CLK2 / Trig_Enable (CSR C000_0004 to C000_0006, C000_000E)

bits <2..0> = *LEphase* [A..E]

bits <13..3> = *LEcounter*

$$LEcounter = \text{floor}\left(\frac{LEdelay - LEOffset}{5TimeStep}\right)$$

$$LEphase = \text{floor}\left(5\left(\frac{LEdelay - LEOffset}{5TimeStep} - LEcounter\right)\right)$$

$$TEcounter = \text{floor}\left(\frac{TEdelay - TEOffset}{5TimeStep} - LEcounter\right)$$

$$TEphase = \text{floor}\left(5\left(\frac{TEdelay - TEOffset}{5TimeStep} - TEcounter - LEcounter\right)\right)$$

TABLE 26. NTA

bit	read meaning	write meaning
<31,30,4..0>	nta bits	set nta bits

- monitoring;
start seq, T1_Y, T1_N, T2_N, T2_Y, start fef, e+, e-, c_bco, w_bco.

4.2 Timing formulas

Definitions:

- *LE* = Leading Edge, *TE* = Trailing Edge
- *LEoffset* and *TEoffset* are the minimal delay
- *TimeStep* = 8.51658 ns (1/rf3)
- *floor(x)* returns the greatest integral value less than or equal to x. This corresponds to IEEE rounding

Table 27: Signal offsets.

Signal	LE Offset (ns)	TE Offset (ns)
WNG0	326.0	420.5
WNG1	326.0	420.5
WNG2	326.0	420.5
WNG3	326.0	420.5
WNG4	803.0	1058.0
CLK0	350.0	
CLK1	350.5	
CLK2	350.5	
Trig_Enable	301.0	

NOTE: Values in Table 27 are average values for the 32 Pandoras. The actual values (in nsec) for each Pandora can be found (after “ONLSETUP Trigger”) in:

PAND2\$DIR:PAND_OFFESTS.DAT

Data are formatted according to:

Pandora#	(I3)
Warnings LEs	(5E16.7)
Warnings TEs	(5E16.7)
Clock LEs	(3E16.7)

See section 4.2 for details on the correspondence CSR content delay value.

Note: $rf3/5 = 42ns$ period.

b2,b1,b0	Phase select
0,0,0	A
0,0,1	B
0,1,0	C
0,1,1	D
1,x,x	E

TABLE 22. CSR C000_000F; current look up table address (loadable up counter)

bit	read meaning	write meaning
<11..0>	T1 look up table pointer/Fastbus address	set T1 look up table pointer/ Fastbus address
<27..16>	T2 look up table pointer	set T2 look up table pointer

Note: When loading the look up table using a fastbus block transfer, the start address for both T1 and T2 look up table, corresponds to the T1 look-up table pointer only.

TABLE 23. CSR C000_0010; (4kx2 SRAM)

bit	read meaning	write meaning
<1..0>	t2 & t1 look up table contents	select t2 & t1 look up table contents

TABLE 24. CSR C000_0011 TO C000_0018; scalers (in the following order): c_bco, gated c_bco, start seq, T1_Y, T1_N, T2_N, T2_Y, fe_rdy;

bit	read meaning	write meaning
<31..0>	read value	none

Attention: every scaler counter reacts directly to the signal on the corresponding input line, i.e. spikes will be counted.

TABLE 25. CSR C000_0019; Account number

bit	read meaning	write meaning
<23..16>	read value	select acc# value

$$\text{nei_done delay} = 7.93 \mu\text{s} + 15.808 \mu\text{s} * \text{value} \langle 7..0 \rangle$$

$$\text{int_oscill_period} = 31.616 \mu\text{s} + 15.808 \mu\text{s} * \sum b_i * 2^{2(i-16)},$$

where: $b_i = 0$ if bit i is off

1 if bit i is on

$$i = 25 \dots 16$$

Note: $\text{rf3}/(29*64) = 15.808 \mu\text{s}$.

Note: Nei_Done delays counters starts counting from T2-Yes leading edge

TABLE 17. CSR C000_000A; wng4 parameters

bit	read meaning	write meaning
<14..0>	present leading edge delay	select leading edge delay
<15>	wng-enable status	0=enable wng, 1=disable wng
<30...16>	present trailing edge delay	select trailing edge delay
<31>	trailing edge disabled	0=enable, 1=disable

See section 4.2 for details on the correspondence CSR content delay value.

Note: $\text{rf3}/29 = 247 \text{ ns period}$.

Note: value 0 for the delay of both LE and TE is not supported

TABLE 18. CSR C000_000B; nei_done mask

bit	read meaning	write meaning
<15..0>	present value of mask	select mask value
<31..16>	current status of inputs	none

TABLE 19. CSR C000_000C; external start trigger mask

bit	read meaning	write meaning
<3..0>	present mask value	select mask

TABLE 20. CSR C000_000D; t2 label latch

bit	read meaning	write meaning
<3..0>	latched t2 label	none

TABLE 21. CSR C000_000E; internal trigger enable delay

bit	read meaning	write meaning
<2..0>	present leading edge phase selection	select leading edge phase
<12..3>	present leading edge delay	select leading edge delay

4.0 Appendices.

4.1 CSR map and bit assignment.

TABLE 9. CSR0; mode control

bits	read meaning	write meaning (bit value)
<2>	stop/running (0/1)	set in run mode
<6>	none	reset scalars
<12>	waiting for csr nei_done	none
<13>	local/global line status (0/1)	set global line (1 = global)
<18>	none	set in stop mode (1)
<28>	none	set csr nei_done (1)
<29>	none	reset global line (0)
<31..16>	Device ID (6907)	none
<30>	none	reset state machine (0)

TABLE 10. CSR 1; source selection, PLL status

bit	read meaning	write meaning
<1,0>	selected start-sequence source	select start_sequence source
<3,2>	selected t1 source	select t1 source
<5,4>	selected t2 source	select t2 source
<7,6>	selected nei_done source	select nei_done source
<8>	PLL0 lock status (unlock = 0)	none
<9>	PLL1 lock status (unlock = 0)	none
<10>	PLL2 lock status (unlock = 0)	none
<11>	selected rf3 source	0 = internal rf3 / 1 = external rf3
<15..12>	state bits S4..S1 of State Machine	none
<21..16>	Pandora Serial Number	none
<23,22>	BCO code	set BCO code '0' for 4 bunches '1' for 8 bunches '2' for 12 bunches '3' for 18 bunches.
<31>	Selected rf3 status ('1' if present)	none

TABLE 8. C6: NEI_DONE

pins(+/-)	contents	I/O
1-2	NEI-DONE(0)	I
3-4	NEI-DONE(1)	I
5-6	NEI-DONE(2)	I
7-8	NEI-DONE(3)	I
9-10	NEI-DONE(4)	I
11-12	NEI-DONE(5)	I
13-14	NEI-DONE(6)	I
15-16	NEI-DONE(7)	I
17-18	NEI-DONE(8)	I
19-20	NEI-DONE(9)	I
21-22	NEI-DONE(10)	I
23-24	NEI-DONE(11)	I
25-26	NEI-DONE(12)	I
27-28	NEI-DONE(13)	I
29-30	NEI-DONE(14)	I
31-32	NEI-DONE(15)	I
33-34	GND	-

TABLE 6. C4: Trigger Decision Lines

pins(+/-)	contents	I/O
1-2	GND	--
3-4	T1-NO	O
5-6	T1-YES	O
7-8	T2-NO	O
9-10	T2-YES	O

TABLE 7. C5: Account Number

pins(+/-)	contents	I/O
1-2	ACC#(0)	O
3-4	ACC#(1)	O
5-6	ACC#(2)	O
7-8	ACC#(3)	O
9-10	GND	--

TABLE 5. C2:Trigger Control Lines

pins(+/-)	contents	I/O
19	GND	--
18-37	----	--
17-36	GND	--
16-35	EXT RF3	I
15-34	GND	--
14-33	EXT W-BCO	I
13-32	EXT C-BCO	I
12-31	E- PICKUP	I
11-30	E+ PICKUP	I
10-29	T1-NO	I
9-28	T1-YES	I
8-27	T2-NO	I
7-26	T2-YES	I
6-25	LABEL(0)	I
5-24	LABEL(1)	I
4-23	----	--
3-22	GND	--
2-21	FE-RDY	O
1-20	GBL	O

3.3.1 Connector signal assignments.

TABLE 3. C1: Wngs and CLKs

pins(+/-)	content	I/O
13	GND	--
12-25	WNG0	O
11-24	WNG1	O
10-23	WNG2	O
9-22	WNG3	O
8-21	WNG4	O
7-20	GND	--
6-19	CLK0	O
5-18	GND	--
4-17	CLK1	O
3-16	GND	--
2-15	CLK2	O
1-14	GND	--

TABLE 4. C3: Local Trigger Control Lines

pins(+/-)	contents.	I/O
1-2	GND	--
3-4	TRIG-ENB	O
5-6	T1-NO-I	I
7-8	T1-YES-I	I
9-10	T2-NO-I	I
11-12	T2-YES-I	I
13-14	GND	--

FIGURE 6. New Pandora front panel.

RF3, BCO leds correspond to the selected sources.

width (time during which the signal is held high, i.e. between “end of start delay” and end of width delay”).

The counters are driven by Fastbus (13 bits in CSR space for WNG0 to WNG3 and 15 bits for WNG4) and are clocked by a 5-phase clock signal derived from rf3 divided by 5 (A, B, C, D and E in the timing diagram of figure 5). For WNG0 to WNG3 the three LSB's of the Fastbus register select the phase. The other bits set the counter timing. The WNG4 is a special long warning which is based on rf3/29, and can cover a time span of ~300 μ s delay and ~220 μ s width.

The division by 5 of the rf3 has been chosen because it is the only one (together with 29) that maintains the phase synchronization with c_bco for all cases of bunch crossing foreseen for LEP (4, 8, 12, 18).

FIGURE 5. Warning circuits.

3.3 Front panel.

The fig.6 shows the front panel (Fastbus width 2), Connector signal assignments are given in section 3.3.1.

- The rf block groups together all the high frequency sections of the Pandora, i.e.: the internal rf3 and c_bco generator (it also generates the internal w_bco) and the three PLLs along with their burst generators.

3.2 RF part.

3.2.1 Phase locked loop.

Each of the PLL daughter board can generate independently clocks with programmed frequency. This choice of implementation is one of the major differences between the new Pandora and the old one. In our implementation the PLL produces frequencies from 5 MHz to about 140 MHz (rf3 is 117.418 MHz). It also allows a finer stepping of the output clock frequencies (i.e. 809 KHz). Figure 4 shows the block diagram of the PLL.

FIGURE 4. Phase lock loop and burst generator.

Fvcm: output frequency from VCM (Voltage Controlled Multivibrator, range 40 to 140 MHz).

Fout: output frequency after division by 2^P ($P=0,1,2,3$).

3.2.2 Warning circuit.

Two counters per warning (fig.5) generate the initial dead time (time during which the warning is held OFF, i.e. between “start delay” and “end of start delay”) and the

3.0 Implementation notes.

3.1 Block diagram.

Fig3. illustrates in more detail the implementation chosen for the new Pandora.

The whole unit can be logically broken down into three blocks:

1. the Fastbus coupler & CSR's block,
2. the control machine block,
3. the rf block.

FIGURE 3. Block diagram.

1. The operating configuration of the Pandora, as well as the internal status, can be controlled via the Fastbus coupler and CSR blocks. The Fastbus also provides the logical interface between the RF and the CONTROL MACHINE sub-units.
2. The control machine contains the state machine that personalizes the use of the Pandora, as well as the generation of the warnings and the delays of the CLK bursts. The state machine also provides the protocol for interfacing the Pandora to Zeus, the FIP and the local trigger box.

- block transfer the data to csr C000_0010 (read or write). An SS2 response will indicate when the end address of the memory has been reached. CSR C000_000F will auto increment on each transfer and will contain at the end of transfer the last memory address accessed.

Random data read/write is also possible, but this will not auto increment the address (CSR C000_000F)

Possible uses:

- if one wants to run the DAQ system locally in a mode where on every start_sequence a readout should occur (t2=yes). This is possible by programming all 1-values in this lookup table and selecting this as a t1/t2 source.
- one can locally control t1 and t2 trigger rates accurately for DAQ tests.
- by loading a random pattern, random t1/t2 trigger sequences can be generated locally.

2.6 Removed features.

With respect to the current Pandora the following features are dropped:

1. internal logic analyzer
2. switchmode operation
3. interleaved cosmic
4. freeze on error
5. programmable delay on external start triggers.

csr1<23,22>. The code will select 4,8,12 or 18 bunch mode for the code values 0,1,2,3.

2.4 Fastbus access.

Only CSR space is implemented, there is no Fastbus data space (DSR). A full map is given in 4.1 where the meaning of the different bit fields is given. Permitted Fastbus data cycles are secondary address read/write, random read/write and hand-shake block transfer read/write (i.e. MS=1)². Only geographical addressing and general broadcast to CSR are supported for primary addressing.

Block transfer is only possible to register C000_0010.

In the run mode only csr 0 and csr C000_0019 can be written to. Writing to other registers is only permitted if the unit is in stop mode. Reading the registers is always possible in any mode.

SS=6 is produced in case of:

- a random data access after a bad NTA was loaded
- an unsupported MS-code during data access
- unauthorized write access to a csr when the module is in run
- a block transfer access to an NTA value different from csr C000_0010

SS=7 is produced when a bad value is loaded in the NTA register.

SS=2 is produced during block transfer, when csr C000_000F reaches a memory address ≥ 4096 .

2.5 Programmable lookup table.

One can use a built-in 4K x 2 bit memory as a table to look up programmed t1/t2 decision sequences. If bit0 is '1' this will produce a t1yes, if '0' a t1no. Similarly, bit1 will produce a t2yes if '1' or a t2no if '0'. T1 and T2 have two independent pointers. During local run the T1 pointer increments at every new start sequence, the T2 pointer increments at every new T1 yes. Register C000_000f contains the memory location that is accessed on the first start_sequence. This register also contains the location which was last accessed during run. In run the memory is used as a circular memory (when reaching the end of memory, the pointers are reset to the start of memory).

To load the lookup table memory one has to proceed as follows;

- load csr C000_000F with the start address in memory (usually 0, but one can start anywhere).

2. IEEE standard FASTBUS 960-1989 and revision IEEE standard FASTBUS 1177-1989

2.2.5 Remark on different modes.

There are no hardware constraints on the possibility to combine different sources for all the signals used by the State Machine (see Fig.2). Some valid combinations that reproduce typical operating modes are given in table 2.

TABLE 2. Some operating modes

Typical operating modes	Pandora selections					
	start-sequence	t1yes	t1no	t2yes	t2no	nei_done
global	w_bco	gbl	gbl	gbl	gbl	any ²
local-normal	c_bco	loc	loc	loc	loc	any
local-random	any ¹	progr	progr	progr	progr	any
local-start	ext_st_trig	progr ³	progr ³	progr ³	progr ³	any
local-confirm	any ¹	ext_conf trigger	default ⁴	always yes	N.A.	any

¹ except w_bco

² except csr bit

³ LUT filled with all “1s” to produce always T1yes and T2yes

⁴ if no ext_conf trigger within the T1_delay, a T1no is generated

2.2.6 Remark on different statuses

When the Run bit is set, the state machine can cycle provided the correct trigger protocol is present.

When the Stop bit is set, the Pandora terminates the current cycle and stops.

Reset bit 30 only resets the state machine to “waiting-for-start-sequence”. The reset is not done automatically by stopping the Pandora.

Global bit produced by the pandora is used in the protocol with Zeus, the C2 connector carries a copy of this bit. The global bit status is independently of the Pandora run/stop status.

2.3 Other internal features.

Internal rf3 generation (crystal oscillator with frequency of 117.418 MHz) can be selected by clearing csr1<11>. This allows the Pandora to function in the absence of external rf3. When internal rf3 is selected, c_bco and w_bco signals are also generated internally. The internal w_bco is the internal c_bco gated by the internal fe_rdy. It is also possible to select the number of bunches using a 2 bit code in

2.2.2 Sources for start_sequence.

The start_sequence is selected with csr1<1,0>. The corresponding 2 bit values are shown below in parentheses

1. warning bco (1,0)
2. clock bco (1,1)
3. external start trigger (0,0)
4. internal oscillator (0,1). This oscillator is programmable (csr C000_0009<25:16>, range 5.525 sec., step 15.808 μ s (rf3/29 * 1/64)). This oscillator permits the emulation of the detector dead time. The start_seq is always initiated by the w_bco following the rising edge of the oscillator.

2.2.3 Sources for T1 and T2.

The selection of the T1 and T2 sources is done by using csr1<3,2> (for T1) and csr1<5,4> (for T2). The corresponding 2 bit values are shown below in parentheses.

1. global T1 and T2 (1,0)
2. local external T1 and T2 (1,1)
3. internal programmed table (0,0) (see section 2.5)
4. external confirm trigger (0,1)

Timings: When T1 and T2 are internally generated; T1 is derived from start_sequence after a programmable delay (csr C000_0008<11:0> range 1.01 ms, step rf3/29 (247 ns), min delay 359 ns). T2 is also derived from start_sequence after a programmable delay (csr C000_0008<30:16>, range 8.094 ms, step rf3/29 (247 ns), min delay 412 ns). Attention: The minimum delay value that the user may put into the csr is 1; if the value is 0 no output is produced.

2.2.4 Sources for nei_done.

The selection of the nei_done source is done by using csr1<7,6>.The corresponding 2 bit values are shown below in parentheses:

1. (1,0) selects the pattern of 16 external inputs, controlled by the contents of csr C000-000B (Nei_Done mask)
2. (1,1) selects the internal source derived from start_sequence after a programmable delay (csr C000_0009, range 4.05 ms, step 15.808 μ s (rf3/29 * 1/64), min delay 24 μ s)
3. (0,0) allows the control of the live time by software. When csr0<12> contains the value '1' the module waits for a nei_done signal. Writing a '1' in bit<28> of csr0 produces this nei_done and clears the bit<12>. The module finishes the cycle and is then again sensitive to new triggers.

2.2 Definition of control state machine.

2.2.1 Basic sequence.

Pandora has one basic sequence of states as drawn schematically in fig.2. The transitions between states are governed by signals that can be selected from a list of possible sources. Different combinations of these sources give different modes of operation (local, global, etc.).

FIGURE 2. basic trigger sequence.

By resetting the module (csr0 <30>) the machine resets to the state 'initialize' and 'wait-for-start-sequence'.

TABLE 1. Electrical signal description

name	I/O	number	type	remarks
w_bco	I	1	diff ecl	
c_bco	I	1	diff ecl	
global	O	1	diff ecl	
gbl_t1no	I	1	diff ecl	
gbl_t1yes	I	1	diff ecl	
gbl_t2no	I	1	diff ecl	
gbl_t2yes	I	1	diff ecl	
fe_rdy	O	1	diff ecl	
rf3	I	1	diff ecl	
t2label	I	2	diff ecl	4 bit bus but only 2 LSB's
e+/e-	I	2	diff ecl	2 bit bus
loc_t1no	I	1	diff ecl	
loc_t1yes	I	1	diff ecl	
loc_t2no	I	1	diff ecl	
loc_t2yes	I	1	diff ecl	
trigger_enable	O	1	diff ecl	
t1no	O	1	diff ecl	selected gbl. or loc.
t1yes	O	1	diff ecl	selected gbl. or loc.
t2no	O	1	diff ecl	selected gbl. or loc.
t2yes	O	1	diff ecl	selected gbl. or loc.
fef	O	1	NIM	
nei_done	I	16	16 diff ecl plus 2 NIM's	masked & ORed together ORed with diff ecl input
warnings	O	5	diff ecl	5 bit bus (last one special)
clocks	O	3	diff ecl	3 bit bus
ext_start_trigger	I	4	diff ecl and NIM's	masked and ORed together
ext_confirm_trigger	I	1	diff ecl and NIM	
monitoring	O	17	NIM's	various test signals
acc number	O	4	diff ecl	4 bit bus

- **warnings 0 - 3:** each warning has a programmable start-delay (csr C000_0000 to C000_0003, range 80 μ s, step 8.5 ns, min-delay 326.0 ns) and programmable width (csr C000_0000 to C000_0003, range 80 μ s, step 8.5 ns, min-delay 94.5 ns); the delays are started by the selected start-sequence source. They are reset by the selected t1-no, t2-no or nei_done. Each warning can be individually disabled by csr C000_000<15> to C000_003<15>.
- **warning 4:** This special warning has a programmable start-delay (csr C000_000A, range 300 μ s, step rf3/29 (247 ns), min-delay 803.0ns) and programmable width (csr C000_000A, range 220 μ s, step rf3/29 (247 ns), min-delay 253.0ns); the delays are started by the selected start-sequence source. They are reset by the selected t1-no, t2-no or nei_done. The warning 4 can be disabled by csr C000_00A<15>.
- **clocks:** each clock can be either free running or burst (csr C000_0004<14> to C000_0006<14>). In this latter case they have a programmable start delay (csr C000_0004<13:0> to C000_0006<13:0>, range 80 μ s, step rf3 (8.5 ns), min-delay 350.0ns) and a programmable number up-to 2^{16} counts (csr C000_0004<31:16> to C000_0006<31:16>). The frequencies that can be generated are given by the following formula:

$$f = N/(M*2^P) * (RF3) \text{ with } M=145 \text{ and for } N=50,\dots,185 \text{ and } P=0,1,2,3$$

- This gives frequencies in a range from 149,809MHz (6.67 ns) down to 5.06 MHz (197.59 ns) (see annexes 4.2 and 4.3). N must always be a multiple of 2^P to keep a constant phase relation to c_bco (i.e. to keep the correct synchronization with LEP).
- A list and more details are found in 4.3
- Each clock can be individually disabled by csr C000_0004<15> to C000_0006<15>
- **t2label:** on every gbl_t2=yes Zeus will generate a 4 bit label. Pandora will latch its 2 LSB's in the right most position of csr C000_000D<3:0>. This feature will be available when Zeus and the Zeus fan-outs are updated.
- **e+ and e-:** these are the discriminated pick-up signals. Pandora receives them on the TCL connector and makes them available on the front panel for precise triggering. This feature will be available when Zeus and the ZEUS fan-outs are updated.

- **loc_t1-yes:** positive first level trigger result. Pandora reacts to its leading edge and will change the current state to ‘wait-for-t2’. Digitizing continues (i.e. the clock and warning signals are not stopped).
- **loc_t2-no:** negative second level trigger result; Pandora reacts to its leading edge and will immediately reset the current state to ‘wait-for-start-sequence’. All clock and warning signals are reset (except the free running clocks).
- **loc_t2-yes:** positive second level trigger result; Pandora reacts to its leading edge and will change the current state to ‘trigger-front-end-freeing’. Digitizing continues (i.e. the clock and warning signals are not stopped).
- **trigger enable:** this signal is asserted after a programmable delay (csr C000_000E, range 80 μ s, step rf3 (8.5 ns), min-delay 301.0 ns) started by the selected start-of-sequence source and deasserted after receiving the selected t1-no or any selected t2.
- **fef:** it is asserted immediately after receiving the selected t2-yes source and deasserted when Pandora receives the selected nei_done.
- **nei_done:** next event identification done signals; 16 inputs to which a programmable don’t-care-mask (csr C000_000B<15:0>) is applied. When all expected inputs are present for more than 50 ns (to avoid spurious glitches) Pandora changes state to ‘reinitialise’. All clock and warning signals are reset (except the free running clocks). Inputs <00> and <01> are an ORed combination between the differential ECL and NIM inputs. The current logical state of these inputs can be read in csr C000_000B<31:16>.
- **external_start_trigger:** 4 input signals with selective enable mask (csr C000_000C). The four external start trigger inputs (NIM and the corresponding ECL are ORed) are ORed after masking. Note that the external start trigger must be synchronous with c_bco, i.e. the pulse must have a constant delay (any allowed, in particular 0) with respect to c_bco¹.
- **external-confirm-trigger:** this signal acts as a loc_t1-yes. After a start_seq the pandora continues to digitize if the external confirm trigger is asserted within a time window specified in csr C000_0008 (internal T1 delay). If the external confirm trigger is not asserted, the Pandora generates an internal t1-no and changes state to “waiting start seq”.
- **monitoring:** Important signals (such as: 5 x wng’s, 3 x clk’s, w_bco, c_bco, e+/e- pick ups, t1_y/n, t2_y/n, fe_rdy) are available on the front panel as NIM. LED’s provide quick visual display of Fastbus access, run mode, global bit, sel. int rf3, sel. ext c_bco, 3 x PLL lock status. More information on the Pandora state is given through CSR’s, see section 4.1.
- **acc number:** This is an internal register (csr C000_0019<23:16>) incremented by selected T2_yes. The 4 LSBs are available on the front panel connector C5, and can be read/written by fastbus.

1. Operatively the delay from c_bco to the ext_start must be programmed (in units of rf3 = 8.51 nsec.) in bit <13..0> of csr C000-0004 (clock0), csr C000-0005 (clock1), csr C000-0006 (clock2).

2.1.1 Signal definitions and their use.

- **c_bco**: clock bco is generated by Zeus; this is an uninterrupted ~100 ns pulse train with the same period as the beam cross over period (i.e. 22 μ s for 4 bunches, 11 μ s for 8 bunches, etc.). Pandora reacts to its leading edge (only this edge is well defined in time).
- **w_bco**: warning bco is generated by Zeus; this pulse train is identical to c_bco (also timing wise) except that it is gated by the “AND” of all the fe_rdy signals coming from all the Pandoras in global. This signal indicates that the detector is ready to accept a new event. Pandora reacts to its leading edge.
- **global**: static signal, it reflects the logic state of bit csr0<13>. This bit needs to be set if the subdetector controlled by this Pandora wants to run in global mode, if bit csr0<13> is set, the “global” signal will be present independent of the run or stop status of the Pandora.
- **gbl_t1-no**: negative first level trigger result; Pandora reacts to its leading edge and will immediately reset the current state to ‘wait-for-start-sequence’. All clock and warning signals are interrupted and reset (except the free running clocks). Pandora will assert fe_rdy immediately. Gbl_t1-no is deasserted by Zeus when the fe_rdys of all Pandoras in global are received.
- **gbl_t1-yes**: positive first level trigger result; Pandora reacts to its leading edge and will change the current state to ‘wait-for-t2’. Digitizing continues (i.e. the clock and warning signals are not stopped). Gbl_t1-yes is deasserted by Zeus when either gbl_t2-no or gbl_t2-yes is asserted.
- **gbl_t2-no**: negative second level trigger result; Pandora reacts to its leading edge and will reset immediately the current state to ‘wait-for-start-sequence’. All clock and warning signals are reset (except the free running clocks). Pandora will assert fe_rdy immediately. Gbl_t2-no is deasserted by Zeus when all fe_rdys of all Pandoras in global are received.
- **gbl_t2-yes**: positive second level trigger result; Pandora reacts to its leading edge and will change the current state to ‘trigger-front-end-freeing’. Digitizing continues (i.e. the clock and warning signals are not stopped). Gbl_t2-yes is deasserted by Zeus when all fe_rdys of all Pandoras in global are received.
- **fe_rdy**: front end ready, only used in global mode, is negated immediately after reception of the w_bco. It is asserted again after gbl_t1-no, gbl_t2-no or the selected nei_done source. The fe_rdy status is the result of the logical AND between state machine “wait-for-start-sequence” and Pandora *run* status (i.e. if Pandora is stopped fe_rdy goes unready).
- **rf3**: radio frequency 3 = lep_rf/3=117,41806 MHz (period about 8.516 ns), used for clock and delay generation.
- **loc_t1-no**: negative first level trigger result. Pandora reacts to its leading edge and will immediately reset the current state to ‘wait-for-start-sequence’. All clock and warning signals are interrupted and reset (except the free running clocks).

2.0 Specifications.

2.1 External connections.

The LTS-CB (Local Trigger Supervisor Control Box or Pandora) is interfaced with several other electronic modules of the DAQ and trigger system. Several signals are exchanged with them.

The basic function of Pandora is to receive the rf3 and bco signals as well as the trigger decisions from Zeus or a local trigger box. It then generates the timing signals for the front end digitizers and the commands for the readout.

The interconnections between these units and Pandora are shown in fig.1, and further description is given in 2.1.1, table 1, and figure 2.

The protocol is illustrated as timing waveforms in 4.5.

FIGURE 1. External connections schematic.

1.0 Introduction.

The new LTS (Local Trigger Supervisor) is a double slot Fastbus (id=6907) for the timing control of the partitions in the Delphi detector. The module consists of a mother board, three PLL, three "Burst", one RF, one Fastbus coupler/State Machine and one Warning/Delay daughter boards:

1. PLL: Synthesizes the clock frequencies,
2. Burst: Produces the burst / free running clocks,
3. RF: Produces the internal RF/3,
4. Fastbus Coupler/State Machine: Fastbus communication and control of the Trigger cycle.
5. Warning/Delay: Produces the programmed warnings and clocks delays.

The role of the LTS is to interface the timing and decision signal derived from Zeus (the Trigger Supervisor) to the individual partition electronics and to supervise the partition data taking either synchronously with the rest of Delphi or in stand alone mode. This new module provides features as similar as it was found possible to the previous. In particular RF2 is no longer available and the delay settings and clocks are based on RF3 (352.2570/3 MHz.) and therefore are in steps of 8.516 nsec (section 4.6.1 contains a list of operational differences between the new and old Pandora, connectivity differences are given in section 4.6.2).

For an updated general description of the Delphi trigger system architecture, see: CERN - ECP / 94-18, IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science Vol42, No 4 (1995) pag 837

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SPECIFICATIONS OF THE NEW DELPHI LTS-CB (PAND2 - F6907)

Rev 4.0

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